

pentacyclic triterpene¹. Mass spectrum of NT-1 exhibited fragments at m/z 444 (M^+), 426 (M^+-H_2O) 411, 383 and 189 (100%). The mass fragmentation pattern coupled with other data suggested its identity with that of dustannin (1)².

In conformity with the structure, 1 formed a monoacetate, $C_{32}H_{54}O_3$ (M^+ 486), m.p. 198–200°, with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Its ir spectra ν_{max} 1 720, 1 250 (O.CO.CH₃) and 3 520 cm^{-1} (tert-hydroxy). The pmr spectra showed besides the usual peaks for methyl and methylene protons, a singlet at δ 2.05 for acetyl functions. The mass spectra exhibited characteristic fragments at m/z 486 (M^+), 426 (M^+-60), 408 ($M^+-60-18$) and 189 (100%) consistent with structure 2. However, final confirmation could not be made for want of authentic sample.

The mass left after extraction chloroform was extracted with methanol at room temperature. Methanol was then removed and the residue partitioned between water and ethyl acetate. Ethyl acetate fraction upon chromatographic purification yielded compound NT-2, $C_{38}H_{60}O_6$ (M^+ 576), m.p. 288–89° [α]_D –33.95° (pyridine), identified as β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside³. It formed an acetate, $C_{43}H_{68}O_{10}$, m.p. 168–70°, [α]_D –23.91° (CHCl₃) and furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 139–40°, on hydrolysis with 5% ethanolic HCl.

- 1; $R_1 = \beta$ -Me, $R_2 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_3 = \alpha$ -OH, $R_4 = R_5 = H$,
 $R_6 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_7 = OH$
 2; $R_1 = \beta$ -Me, $R_2 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_3 = \alpha$ -OAc, $R_4 = R_5 = H$,
 $R_6 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_7 = OH$
 3; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_7 = H$, $R_4 = \beta$ -Me, $R_5 = \alpha$ -Me,
 9,11-dehydro

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of rhizomes of *N. tuberosa* afforded compound NT-3, $C_{30}H_{50}$ (M^+ 410), m.p. 167–70°, which exhibited in its mass spectrum, besides the molecular ion peak, other prominent peaks at m/z 395, 257, 243 (100%) and 231. The base peak at m/z 243 coupled with the appearance of a one-proton multiplet at δ 5.4 suggested its identity as fern-9(11)-ene (3)⁴ which was finally confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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Flavonoids from the Leaves of *Buchanania lanzan* (Anacardiaceae)

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IN consideration of interesting biological properties of many species¹ of *Buchanania* rich in flavonoid constituents, investigation on flavonoid constituents of several species² of this genus was undertaken. In the present paper we report the isolation and characterisation of kaempferol-7-*O*-glucoside (BLG-I), quercetin-7-*O*-rhamnoside (BLG-II) and quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoglucoside (BLG-III) along with quercetin (BL-I), gallic acid (BL-II) and kaempferol (BL-III) which were characterised by their spectral data and comparison with authentic samples.

The leaves (1 kg; collected from Dudh Sagar, Goa) were consecutively extracted with petroleum ether, benzene, acetone and methanol. The acetone extract gave positive colour test for flavonoids. The tlc examination (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, B-P-F, 36:9:5) revealed the presence of three bands which were labelled as BL-I to BL-III in the order of increasing R_f values. They were separated by preparative-tlc (B-P-F) and eluted by acetone. BL-I, m.p. 313–14°; BL-II, m.p. 250 and BL-III, m.p. 276–78°, were characterised as quercetin, gallic acid and kaempferol, respectively, by comparison of their R_f values, m.p., m.m.p., uv, ir and nmr spectra with authentic samples.

The methanol extract on tlc examination (chloroform-methanol-water; 35 : 13.5 : 1.8) showed three brown spots under uv light. They were separated by preparative-tlc and labelled as BLG-I to BLG-III, in order of increasing R_f values.

Compound BLG-I: It was crystallised from methanol-benzene as yellow cubes, m.p. 228°. Shinoda and Molisch test showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone, m.p. 276–78°, characterised as kaempferol by comparison of its m.p., uv and nmr spectra with that of authentic sample. The sugar was found to be glucose by R_f values on co-pc with authentic sugars. BLG-I showed a slight hypsochromic shift while its aglycone revealed a bathochromic shift of 9 nm (from 266 to 275 nm) with NaOAc, showing the attachment of sugar at C-7 of the kaempferol. The identity of BLG-I as kaempferol-7-*O*-glucoside was further supported by the hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside. The partial methyl ether obtained was identified as 3', 4', 5'-trimethoxykaempferol by m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic sample (m.p. 151°)⁶.

Compound BLG-II: It was a yellow solid, m.p. 272° and gave positive Shinoda and Molisch test. On acid hydrolysis, it gave an aglycone, m.p. 315° and a sugar. The aglycone was identified as quercetin by direct comparison with an authentic sample and also by uv spectral studies. The sugar was identified as rhamnose by co-pc with authentic sugars. The uv spectral data of BLG-II showed the presence of free 3-OH, 5-OH and 3',4'-orthodihydroxyl groups with classical shift reagents. Hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside gave 3,5,3',4'-tetramethylquercetin⁶, m.p. 284°, and was characterised by comparison with an authentic sample. The formation of the above tetramethyl ether confirmed the attachment of sugar at C-7 hydroxyl group. BLG-II was thus characterised as quercetin-7-*O*-rhamnoside.

Compound BLG-III: It was a bright yellow solid, m.p. 191–92° and gave positive Shinoda and Molisch test. The uv spectral data in the presence of classical shift reagents indicated the presence of free hydroxyl groups at C-5 and C-7 besides 3',4'-orthodihydroxyl groups⁷ and glycosylation at C-3. Total hydrolysis of BLG-III with 10% alcoholic HCl gave quercetin, glucose and rhamnose, and was identified by R_f value, m.p., m.m.p. spectral data and co-pc with authentic samples. The partial hydrolysis of BLG-III with 1% aqueous H₂SO₄ for 1 h gave a glucoside, BLG-III_{pg} and rhamnose. BLG-III_{pg} on further hydrolysis yielded quercetin and glucose thereby indicating rhamnose to be the terminal sugar. Methylation of BLG-III by Hakomori's method followed by acid hydrolysis gave 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-1-rhamnose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-glucose and an aglycone characterised as quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether (m.p. 193°). On the basis of the above facts BLG-III was characterised as quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoglucoside (rutin).

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2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole as an Analytical Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(III)

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THE title compound gives dark red colour with iron(III), the intensity of which is not affected by the ions which generally cause interference in case of other reagents reported¹. The 1 : 2 (metal-reagent) complex absorbs at λ 480 nm, away from the absorbance maxima of the reagent itself (450 nm). The reagent is very sensitive and the determination straightforward, which is an indication of the betterment in the direction of the search of a more suitable reagent for iron(III) determinations in micro analysis.

The reagent was synthesised as reported earlier². Sodium nitrite (1.4 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in water (25 ml) was gradually added to a well-cooled solution of aniline (1.85 g, 0.02 mol) in 3 *N* HCl (2.5 ml). The diazonium salt solution was filtered to a cold suspension of 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (3.5 g, 0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (5 g) in ethanol (50 ml). After constant stirring for 0.5 h the mixture was left for 2 h. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-phenylazothiazole precipitated was filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised as red needles from DMF-ethanol mixture (1 : 1), m.p. 195°.

Absorbance measurements at varying wavelengths were recorded with a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer using 1-cm path-length matched glass cuvettes. pH measurements were made with a ECIL 823 pH meter.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 100–400 μ g of iron(III) was added 0.01 *M* reagent (1.0 ml) and then diluted to 25 ml with the buffer solution (pH 3.0; sodium acetate-HCl). The absorbance was measured at 480 nm using ethanol as reference.

Vosburgh and Cooper's method³ indicated the formation of only one complex and the presence